

ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH 100 MOST CITED PUBLICATIONS

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Abstract

There is a rising interest in organisational commitment in today's global world. This study aims to examine knowledge base of the vastly cited publications on organisational commitment by the use of science mapping. It aims to create a picture of the existing knowledge of the field with the influential authors, countries, journals and keywords. Bibliometric analysis has been done on the 100 mostly cited publications out of the total results numbering 6525, generated on SCOPUS database. VOSviewer software has been used to conduct analyses for citation, co-citation amongst authors, countries and keyword co-occurrence. The results depict that although research on organisational commitment (OC) is of growing interest globally, contribution from Eastern and Asian countries has been scarce. The analysis identifies John P. Meyer, followed by Natalie Allen, as eminent contributors to highly cited publications. The most analysed topics in organisational commitment are "job satisfaction", "psychological aspect", and "organisation". Analysis of top journals reveal that all journals which have contributed to the 100 most frequently cited publications stand highly ranked. This analysis has been carried out by using only the SCOPUS database. Identification of core research and key concepts help future scholars in the arena of OC. As the review of the literature suggests, no bibliometric analysis on OC has hitherto been conducted. This paper will serve as a guide to future researchers and practitioners through science mapping of the prevailing knowledge and advancing future knowledge in the arena.

Keywords: Bibliometric, Organisational Commitment, Science Mapping, Vosviewer, Most Cited, Co-Citation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organisational commitment (OC) is a subject of widespread research over the last 50 years due to its importance in organisations. In today's competitive environment, organisations wish to gain competitive advantage through applications of this concept as numerous studies have shown commitment to being a key variable in understanding employees' behaviour resulting in performance (Mishra, Shukla & Sujatha, 2021). Organisational commitment is defined as the employees' relative degree of allegiance and attachment towards the organisations they work in (Porter, Steers, Mowday, & Boulian, 1974). Porter, Steers, Mowday, and Boulian (1974) described OC in with three parts- first being employees having strong conviction as well as alignment with the organization's goals and values, the second with being a ready to put in significant effort for the organization, and the third with having a clear intention to remain a part of the organization. Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch and Topolnytsky (2002) have conceptualised and differentiated components of OC into three forms: affective, normative and continuance. Such categorisation has been considered the leading model in research on OC (Klein, Molloy, & Brinsfield, 2012). Most of OC research has been carried out using social exchange theory (Khoreva, 2016), social identity theory (Presbitero, Newman, Le, Jiang, & Zheng, 2019) or

through attitudinal and behavioural approach (WeiBo, Kaur, & Jun, 2010) as well as a multi-dimensional approach (Jasiwal, Raychaudhuri, & Akhtar, 2020; Meyer & Allen, 1991). Organisational commitment influences employees' behaviour and is a critical element for businesses to attain maximum efficiency and success. Employees are more likely to put effort into their work if they believe their employer understands and supports their psychological need to feel protected. Therefore, members of organisation with a high level of commitment have also shown an increase in their engagement, reduced absenteeism and less intention to leave the organisation (Choi, Tran, & Park, 2015; Lambert, Griffin, Hogan, & Kelley, 2015). A high level of OC has also been linked with job satisfaction (Abou Hashish, 2017). In the current scenario, the concept of OC has become the focus of HR professionals, as it is deemed a predictor of employee turnover and retention (Sathyanarayan & Lavanya, 2018). Thus, this concept has established its importance and relevance for both employees as well as the organisation. Many studies have been done and are being done on the topic of OC, which is one of the important phenomena that allows firms to achieve competitive advantage in today's modern business strategy. Scholars' interest in organisational commitment exists now and is expected to endure in the future. This has resulted in a large volume of publications the world over.

Several meta-analyses have been done to analyse the antecedents and the outcomes of OC (Choi & Colbert, 2015; Guzeller & Celiker, 2019). Ample number of review articles have been written summarizing the concept of OC (Cohen, 2007; Maydiantoro, et al., 2020; Srirangam Ramaprasad, Prabhu, Lakshminarayan, & Pai, 2017; Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016). Such reviews have improved readers' understanding of OC. However, such reviews have several limitations such as limited sample size, subjective bias and lack of rigour. Moreover, the intrinsic nature of the concept of OC itself is dynamic and is developing with the whirligig of time which qualitative reviews are unable to portray adequately. Throughout the last few decades, the number of articles introducing, measuring, analysing and operationalising OC have increased rapidly, which necessitates appropriate analysis for understanding the progress of knowledge in this area. Given the quantity of the number of research works published in this area, it is imperative to examine the intellectual structure along with the traits of the field, which purportedly can be fulfilled through a bibliometric analysis.

The bibliometric review fills the research gap by providing an impartial assessment of the field. Researchers can trail the development path of a matter and perform comprehensive examination with the help of bibliometrics (Fellnhöfer, 2019). Reviewing current knowledge in an area allows to grasp the major themes and theoretical approaches, as well as identify gaps and crucial prospects for ongoing development.

To check whether any bibliometric study has been conducted on the topic of OC a search query was generated on SCOPUS on 20th March 2022 with the parameters "Organisation commitment" and "Bibliometric". This query resulted in total 9 results and none of these studies had analysed the 100 maximum cited articles on OC. One of the articles with utmost relevance was authored by Heras-Rosas, Herrera, and Rodríguez-Fernández (2021) which was limited to the healthcare sector whereas this study aims to look at Organisational Commitment in all its connotations. Another article which was found in this search was by Herrera and Las Heras-Rosas (2021) which was focused on the research pertaining to psychological contract and OC and their

relationship. The rest of the articles were much different from the objectives of this study. As has been seen, a bibliometric study in the OC field is still scarce.

In this study science mapping method based on bibliometric analysis was adopted using VOSviewer software. To generate a greater understanding of the field of OC, this study was carried out to examine and analyse the publication trends and citations, the contributions and collaborations of countries, the pattern of contributing scholars and author co-citation, frequently used keywords by authors, as well as the top journals of the 100 most frequently cited publications on organisational commitment (OC).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The bibliometric analysis constructs structural pictures of scientific fields using bibliographic data from publishing databases. Researchers use bibliometric analysis in quantitative evaluation to improve the understanding of the most important contributions, linkages among prominent authors, major themes, widely cited papers, and citation structure in the top prominent journals. Bibliometric analysis has been conducted in diverse areas of research in management and business (Baker, Pandey, Kumar, & Haldar, 2020; Khan & Mukhtar, 2020; Zhang, Hou, Yang, Yang, & Wang, 2021). Most cited articles for bibliometric analysis have also been used in the arena of business and management (Gholampour, Gholampour, & Noruzi, 2022; Moosa & Shareefa, 2020). Science mapping is utilized to delineate the structure and development of a research field (Zupic & Čater, 2015). The intellectual links within a discipline of highly dynamic bibliographic information can be studied via science mapping, which is an important approach in bibliometric analysis. Many researchers have conducted bibliometric analysis using VOSviewer software (Abdullah & Othman, 2022; Apriliyanti & Alon, 2016; Bartolacci, Caputo, & Soverchia, 2020; Ozturk, 2020). The bibliometric analysis tool used in this study was through VOSviewer software.

2.1 Data Search and Identification

Numerous online database sources are available which are utilised for searching, taking out and analysing data for bibliometric analysis. Some significant and commonly used databases are SCOPUS, Web of Science (WOS) and Google Scholar (Cobo, López-Herrera, Herrera-Viedma, & Herrera, 2012). Elsevier's SCOPUS database was selected for carrying out this study as the data source for the selection of publications as it is the largest database for abstracts and citations and is more reliable (Franceschini, 2016). Furthermore, SCOPUS is regarded as one of the highly comprehensive databases for the area (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016) which is a compelling rationale for using it as the primary source of bibliometric data for this study. The data was gathered on 25th March 2022 using the term "Organisational Commitment" with restrictions to article title, abstract and keywords. The following string was then utilized for the final search: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("organisational commitment") AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "PSYC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "MULT")). No time period was specified because only the number of citations of articles was considered. Only articles were considered and books, book chapters, conference proceedings and reviews were excluded from the search. Documents published in only the English language were included. Research on

organisational commitment has been done in many fields such as Sociology, Psychology, Business and management and Economics. Therefore, these fields were included in the screening of documents. This search resulted in 6525 documents, which were thereafter sorted by the number of citations from highest to lowest.

2.2 Data Extraction and Cleaning

Based on the above parameters, the search identified 6525 articles which were downloaded as comma-separated values (.csv) file. As for this study, only data from the top 100 mostly cited articles was required, a separate file containing all bibliometric data for the top mostly cited 100 articles was downloaded. A data cleaning procedure was then conducted to check for inadequate, duplicate or wrongly selected entries. Verification of the fields (columns) was done to check for any missing or incomplete data and cross-checking of the content with the field title was done to ensure alignment of data. All wrong entries were then deleted accordingly.

2.3 Data Analysis

For the purposes of this research, the authors applied analysis of citation and co-citation, analysis of co-authorship, as well as analysis of keyword co-occurrence using VOSviewer. There are quite a few softwares available for science mapping such as HistCite (Syed Hamad Hassan Shah, 2019), Gephi (Fahimnia, Sarkis, & Davarzani, 2015), Bibexcel (Baker, Pandey, Kumar, & Haldar, 2020), CiteSpace (Li, Ma, & Qu, 2017) and VOSviewer (Donthu, Kumar, & Pattnaik, 2020). In this study, VOSviewer was utilised for the visualisation of bibliometric maps/networks. Moreover, Microsoft Excel was used for creating graphs for trend analysis. There are several ways to visualise science mapping which are widely used by researchers, viz. those based on distance or graph or timeline (Van Eck & Waltman, 2014). VOSviewer creates distance-based graphs (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010), which can furthermore depict the edges, if needed, and hence was applied in this study (Van Eck & Waltman, 2014).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Pattern of Publications and citations

Figure 1 depicts the graphical depiction of the distribution of 100 mostly cited articles and the normalized average citations over the years. The graph reveals the growth of the number of publications on organisational commitment which has increased over the years. With just 3 publications in 1974, there was a steady increase to 361 publications in 2017. There can be observed a boost in publications after 2005, which was constantly on the rise until 2017. The most cited publications on OC were published between the years 1974-2017. The number of years elapsed since publication was used to normalise the average citations. The number of mostly cited articles seemed to reduce post 2007; however, the normalised average citation kept on rising. This decrease might be because of the time taken for an article to generate adequate citations. Moreover, the line of normalised average citation is constantly above the amount of mostly cited articles which shows a persistent interest of researchers in the topic of OC. With the boost in the quantum of publications in the last few years, it is highly predictable that the number of mostly cited articles will increase in the coming years. The sheer number of times articles have been published does not per se indicate the value and effect of research put forward. Often the citations of a paper are commonly used to gauge the research work. A published paper is generally considered influential if cited by many authors.

Figure 1: Total number of articles vs. the number of articles in 100 most cited articles

Note: Only those years in which there has been an occurrence of at least one paper from the 100 most highly cited articles have been shown in the graph.

3.2 Contribution and Collaboration of countries

Figure 2: Contribution of various countries in 100 most cited publications

For analysis of the contribution of countries who have published the mostly cited articles, data was cleaned where any country was not explicitly mentioned. The results indicated that there were 17 countries in total. Figure 2 shows countries which had the highest contribution to the highest cited articles.

As shown, the most noteworthy contribution was from the United States (51.75%) accounting for half of the most cited literature with Canada coming in next with 19.3%.

Since the concept of organisational commitment was first introduced in America, researchers led this field. The west had largely been dominant in this arena as the top two countries (Canada and the USA) together added 71.05% of publications.

European countries had also contributed 16.67% to the topic, whereas Asian countries had only 7.02% contribution to the literature and only one paper had been included from Africa. Despite a few numbers of papers, Asian and African countries surfaced in the 100 most cited articles which augurs well for research in these countries.

To examine the pattern of collaboration among countries, co-authorship analysis was used on VOSviewer. The nodes in such network maps which depict keywords are located by minimising a function that is conditional on the similarity measurements (AS_{ij}) between nodes (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010). (AS_{ij}) explains itself as

$$AS_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{C_i C_j}$$

C_{ij} denotes the number of times the terms 'i' and 'j' appear in a text, whereas C_i and C_j denote the predicted number of times the keywords 'i' and 'j' appear together. The results of the collaborations between countries among the 100 most frequently cited articles of OC are depicted in Figure 3 which portrays that 14 out of 17 countries emerged in a collaboration network. The Netherlands had the maximum number of collaborations with 6 countries. But when the highest link strength was considered both USA and Netherlands came out on top with the total link strength of 7.

In second place Canada, the UK and Hong Kong were seen with the second highest collaboration based on link strength (link strength = 6). However, the UK and Hong Kong gained the second position when the number of links was considered (number of links = 5). Since every author has a different point of view, a combined effort can broaden the knowledge base of the field. There is a vast scope of research across borders and geographical locations. These results portray the significance of collaboration at international level and their input in generating mostly cited publications.

Figure 3: Collaborations between countries among 100 most cited publications

Note: The minimum number of publications required by each country was set at 1. Terms which were not actual country names were left out of the analysis. Only 14 countries out of 17 emerged in some collaborations that are presented in the network.

3.3 Contributing Scholars and Author co-citation

Another aim of this study was to scrutinise the most contributing scholar and author co-citation who has produced the most cited papers on OC literature. Table 1 depicts the names of most contributing scholars.

Table 1: Most contributing scholar in the 100 most cited publications

Rank	Authors	Scopus Articles	Citations	Total Link Strength
1	Meyer J.P.	10	21711	35
2	Allen N.J.	5	10295	30
3	Eisenberger R.	4	7319	8
4	Schaufeli W.B.	4	3387	5

As Table 1 portrays, four 4 scholars contributed the most to the topic of OC. There were overall 208 authors who had contributed in the list of the most cited publications, out of which only 4 authors met the threshold of having a minimum of 4 documents. As depicted in Table 1 Meyer had the highest contribution with 10 publications with a citation of 21711, followed by Allen with 5 documents, Eisenberger with 4 and Schaufeli with 4.

The total link strength in the table shows collaborations among authors who had contributed to 100 most cited publications. Meyer had the highest collaborations, whereas Schaufeli had the least collaborations among the scholars. Moreover, even though Eisenberg and Schaufeli contributed the same number of publications to the most cited articles, Eisenberg had significantly more citations than Schaufeli.

Figure 4: Author co-citation network

Figure 4 indicates a co-citation map based on the 100 mostly cited articles on organisational commitment. Analysis of author co-citation creates the intellectual structure immanent in the field and helps to identify and connect authors and their writings (Zupic & Čater, 2015). When two authors are co-cited together it shows a similarity in the intellectual quality of their works (Small, 1973).

For this analysis, a minimum of 20 citations was used as the criterion which resulted in a response of 52 authors. The relative frequency of author co-citation is depicted by the size of the nodes. Authors in close proximity resemble a higher similarity in their intellectual structure. As portrayed in Figure 4, the frequently cited publications can be grouped into four different clusters of colours. The most prominent cluster is the green cluster consisting of scholars Meyer, Allen and Steers whose works are pivotal in organisational commitment literature focusing on the categorisation of OC into affective, continuance and normative commitment and their measurement.

The size and the distance between the nodes represent their influence over the field and the closeness of their research works respectively. The red cluster represents scholars such as Ashforth and Judge, whose work was focused on social support for newcomer employees. The blue cluster represents research on the antecedents and outcomes of commitment by authors such as Cropanzano and Luthans. The yellow cluster is far away from the rest of the clusters depicting their works were different and not closely related to the rest of the clusters. It may be pertinent to mention that scholars in this cluster, such as Bakker and Schaufeli have focused on work engagement and burnout.

3.5 Co-occurrence of Keywords

Keywords co-occurrences analysis can determine the popular themes in OC literature. In this study also analysis of co-occurrence of keywords was carried out which is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 5: Authors' keyword co-occurrence network

A search was conducted to find the key themes which researchers have focused on in the 100 most cited publications. VOSviewer generated a total of 256 keywords. When a minimum of 3 co-occurrences was set, out of 256 keywords only 32 keywords met the requirements. Both authors and index keywords assigned by journals were used. Words such as “articles”, “meta-analysis”, “organisational commitment”, “human” and “humans” were omitted from the thesaurus file for this analysis. The main

concepts resulting from the keywords could be classified into three clusters which are portrayed in Figure 5.

According to the clusters, the major keywords in each one of the three clusters are “job satisfaction”, “psychological aspect”, and “organisation”. These terms appear to be strongly linked to OC as they represent the diverse conceptual frameworks which are commonly utilised in the OC literature to describe the phenomena related to this intriguing gamut of study. The keywords are closely related to the study of antecedents as well as the consequences of OC. In the red cluster, the most repeated keyword with a frequency of 10 is “job satisfaction”. It also has a high link strength of 5 with another keyword “personnel management” within the same cluster. The concepts related to “personnel turnover”, “employment”, “personality”, and sex-related effects of organisational commitment all belong to the same cluster. Strategies for Employee Engagement and Retention are the main theme here. By examining factors such as hiring procedures, character traits, and personnel administration techniques, this area offers an emphasis on how businesses effectively manage people to increase employee satisfaction, lower attrition, and strengthen organisational commitment.

The mostly occurring keyword in the green cluster is “psychological aspect” with a frequency of 7. As can be found in the results, “psychological aspect” has links with “psychological theory”, “clinical trial”, “burnout”, “work engagement”, “social support” and “performance” within the workplace (link strength ranging from one to four). It also has a high association (link strength of 4) with “human relation” which belongs to the blue cluster. The theme for this cluster is Psychological Determinants. This theme suggests looking into the connections between worker performance and organisational commitment as well as a range of psychological traits like burnout, work engagement, social support, and underlying psychological theories. It most likely involves examining the psychological mechanisms that impact employees' allegiance to their employers and the ways in which these factors relate to overall job performance outcomes.

As can be seen, the keywords “organisation”, “organisational culture”, “human relation”, “interpersonal relations” and “leadership” form the blue cluster. The most significant keyword of this cluster is “organisation” having a frequency of 9 and has high link strength of 7 with “organisational culture”. This depicts the researchers' attention to culture within an organisation. As found in existing literature researchers in most cited publications have focused on human relations at different levels through OC. The theme derived in this cluster is Organisational Environment and Commitment. This theme calls for an examination of the ways in which organisational components such as culture, human relations, leadership styles, and interpersonal dynamics impact how devoted workers are to their employers. It probably means looking into the ways that organisational cultures, structures, and leadership philosophies affect workers' attitudes, behaviours, and views of their loyalty to the company. This illustrates the researchers' focus on organisational culture.

3.6 Top Journals

Table 2 portrays the top journals which have published the top 100 most cited publications.

Table 2: Top journals on the 100 most cited publications

No.	Journals	Total Publications	Total Citations	Citation Per Publication	Cite Score ^a	SNIP ^a	SJR ^b
1	Journal of Applied Psychology	31	31704	1022.71	12.3	4.18	Q1, 6.52
2	Journal of Management	8	6649	831.12	21.4	5.75	Q1,7.49
3	Academy of Management Journal	6	3978	663	14.2	4.23	Q1, 11.19
4	Journal of Vocational Behavior	6	10758	1793	8.4	2.80	Q1, 2.61
5	Journal of Organisational Behavior	5	3356	671.2	11.8	3.59	Q1, 3.94
6	Personnel Psychology	4	4409	1102.25	10.6	3.71	Q1, 6.08
7	Leadership Quarterly	3	2871	957	13.2	4.32	Q1, 4.99
8	Human Resource Management Review	2	5603	2801.5	11	3.37	Q1, 2.55
9	International Journal of Human Resource Management	2	1248	624	6.9	1.84	Q1, 1.38
10	Journal of Managerial Psychology	2	2339	1169.5	3.1	1.06	Q1, 0.88
11	Journal of Marketing	2	929	464.5	12.3	3.83	Q1, 7.8
12	Journal of Occupational Psychology	2	6128	3064	5.1	1.60	Q1, 2.25
13	Organisational Behavior and Human Decision Processes	2	2352	1176	4.6	2.10	Q1, 2.68
14	Psychological Bulletin	2	3615	1807.5	38.8	11.50	Q1, 10.74
15	Work and Stress	2	1705	852.5	7.7	2.68	Q1,1.91

Note: SNIP = Source Normalised Impact per Paper; SJR = Scimago journal ranking; ^a Figures for 2021 provided by SCOPUS; ^b Figured for 2021 provided by ScimagoJR

The results depict that there were a total of 36 journals which had published minimum one article in the 100 mostly cited publications. However, only 15 journals had contributed either equal to or at least two articles in the hundred most cited publications. These 15 journals have been shown in Table 2 in descending sequence of the number of documents published. The most forthright analysis which can be seen from the table was that all journals are ranked in Q1 by ScimagoJR. This indicated that almost all highly cited articles on OC came from top ranked journals.

As indicated from the table above, the journal “Journal of Applied Psychology” whose first volume was published in 1917, was most active in the arena with 31 publications. Moreover, one article from this journal was the third mostly cited article on the topic of OC with 3995 citations. As can be seen, no journal except the “Journal of Applied Psychology” had more than 8% of the most cited publications, which indicated that limited journals have specialised explicitly in the field of OC.

CiteScore, a Scopus alternative to the Clarivate Analytics Impact Factor (JCR), is a statistic for assessing journal impact based on Scopus citation data. The journal's influence is measured by its citation score. In terms of CiteScore and SNIP, the journal “Psychological Bulletin” has the highest values, yet it had contributed a lesser quantity of publications to the 100 most cited publications within the area of OC. This might be due to authors sending papers to journals with publishing scope and with an eye on the purview of the journal itself.

4. DISCUSSION

This study provides an overview which can help in systematic literature reviews in future. The results present some interesting findings. First, the topic of OC has been of strong interest to scholars which can be seen by the increase in publications and citations. Second, it is safe to assume that interest in this field will go on to rise in the upcoming years, taking into account the rise in literature over the past decade.

Analysis of the publication patterns of highly cited papers revealed that the maximum cited publications had been from 1974 to 2017 and thereafter 58 out of 100 most frequently cited publications had been published in or after the year 2000. Further analysis of the collaborations and contributions of countries unveiled that more than half of the 100 most cited publications were from the United States. Hong Kong came out to be the highest contributor in Asia. The research findings suggest that Asian countries were lacking in publications and high citations. This indicates the need for studying organisational commitment from a non-western perspective.

Even though there is a continual surge in the number of publications within the field, yet only a few author names were dominant. Meyer, Allen, Eisenberg and Schaufeli were some of the most prominent authors in the field. Meyer and Allen had worked on the conceptualisation of OC and creating a measurement scale (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Meyer & Allen, 1991; Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch, & Topolnytsky, 2002). On the other hand, work by Eisenberg and Schaufeli was focused on perceived organisational support (Eisenberger, Fasolo, & Davis-LaMastro, 1990; Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, & Sowa, 1986) burnout and work engagement (Bakker, Schaufeli, Leiter, & Taris, 2008; Hakonen, Bakker, & Schaufeli, 2006). The analysis also revealed that Meyer was the highest contributor in this field with the highest citation. Analysis of author co-citation and analysis of keyword co-occurrence also unveiled the intellectual structure of the field and the most prominent themes of the literature respectively. As shown in Figure 5, “job satisfaction”, “psychological aspect” and “organisation” were widely researched keywords with themes evolving from them like “Strategies for Employee Engagement and Retention”, “Psychological Determinants” and “Organisational Environment and Commitment”. This depicts scholars’ interest in antecedents of commitment such as job satisfaction, attitude, and demographic factors as well as its outcomes such as performance, work engagement and burnout. It also shows focus on predictors which may be interpersonal or contextual such as leadership, interpersonal relations, and organisational culture. This finding is consistent with Bogler & Berkovich (2020) which determined three themes in commitment among teachers. There can be seen an interlinkage between the most prominent authors and the majorly studied themes. Furthermore, it is also found that highly ranked journals contribute immensely to the most cited publications. “Journal of Applied Psychology” took the lead and published 31% of the 100 most highly cited articles. It can, therefore, be deduced that for a research to be widely cited, it should also be published in a journal with a high impact factor and is highly ranked. It may be also pertinent to note that majority of the top journals are related to business and management, while some are from the field of psychology.

The present bibliometric study has been constrained by some limitations. When obtaining the bibliometric data, a single database i.e., Elsevier’s SCOPUS was exclusively used. Citation and Co-citation analysis used in this study were susceptible to some limitations. They did not depict the context and purpose behind the citation. It

only presented the patterns of citation and the development of the field based on such citations. Also, when acquiring the list of 100 most cited publications, the citation count of each article was used. This might suggest a preference for older articles when compared with newer articles regardless of their quality and content. Recently published works showed fewer citations and importance when compared with older studies. Additionally, this study was limited due to missing data such as keywords and references for some publications. Finally, since this analysis was limited to 100 most frequently cited publications, the results might be much different, if all publications found in the original search are considered for analysis.

5. CONCLUSION

The effects of organisational commitment on competitive advantage and performance have piqued the curiosity of scholars over time. The science mapping of the extensive literature on organisational commitment has revealed several significant findings from the most cited and influential authors, countries, journals, and key themes. Scholars looking forward to conducting research in this area can obtain assistance from the current study regarding trending schools of thought, the important themes which have been studied over the years, which journal to publish in, and the important keywords for taking up the research. Researchers in the discipline can explore inter-relationships among different themes and also take up less studied topics emerging out of the study for greater research. The keywords identified can help scholars write articles which have a high possibility of getting cited. The present study found three main themes which were Employee engagement and retention, psychological determinants and third theme was Organisational environment and commitment. Moreover, since majority of the cited articles were from the United States, more international collaborations among authors can aid the growth and development of the literature. The study can also benefit organisational policymakers and implementers as it enunciates the most studied themes under the head of organisational commitment which can portray concomitant importance in organisational practice. They can design and implement human resource policies and schemes which can lead to augmentation of commitment resulting in the fruition of organisational objectives.

Ethical considerations

Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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